

Project
Newsletter

Fulvio Mascari (ENEA)
Fabio Giannetti (UNIROMA1)

Funded by the
European Union

Welcome in the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Project Newsletter

Nowadays Light Water cooled SMR (LW-SMR) are one of the key design options for the near-term deployment of nuclear reactor technology due to their generally recognized advantages (inherent safety, design simplicity, possibility of simplified batch production, reduction of construction time, reduce capital and operational cost, etc.) and to their level of technological and licensing readiness.

The advanced technological and licensing readiness of LW-SMR is a result of starting from the well-proven-established operating Large-Light Water Reactor (L-LWR) technology, incorporating their operational plant experience/feedback, and including moderate evolutionary design modifications to increase the inherent safety of the plant. Therefore, it is envisaged to benefit from the operating L-LWR knowledge and know-how as a base of the SMR technology, minimizing the technological risks connected with innovative technological solutions proposed in innovative SMRs (that differ significantly from existing operating reactors). Therefore, several LW-SMR concepts are in an advanced design state and ready to be licensed. Construction and certification activities are currently on-going and are expected to further increase and accelerate.

Considering the Net Zero Goal by 2050 in Europe and European competitiveness, nuclear energy will have a key role in reaching this target with the aim of contributing to decarbonization in Europe. In view of the envisaged short-term license process in European countries, an R&D program consistent with the European market needs and

license requirements is in progress to ensure the implementation of the highest nuclear safety standards. In this regard, the safety demonstration is the key action to confirm the adequacy of the safety provisions ensuring the stable and safe operation of an SMR in all the plant states.

Within this framework, Euratom Research and Training Programs have a key role in supporting R&D activities, speeding-up licensing process, and securing a leading position for European Institutions within the international framework. European projects are articulated addressing different topics, in order to support the expected safety demonstration of LW-SMR in Europe, and different actions are in progress or have been recently finished (e.g. ELSMOR, HARMONISE, MCSAFER, PASTELS, SASPAM-SA, TANDEM, EASI-SMR).

In this framework, the systematic analyses of the applicability and transfer of the current available SA experimental database (developed for current large-LWR) for iPWR safety assessment studies, and the analyses of current codes capabilities to simulate SA phenomena in iPWR are novel topics of current high interests for TSOs, regulators, research centres, universities, industries and operators and are addressed in SASPAM-SA project. The project is coordinated by ENEA (Italy) and twenty-three Organizations from fourteen Countries are involved: ENEA, CIEMAT, CNRS, EDF, FZJ, GRS, INRNE, IRSN, KIT, KTH, LEI, POLIMI, RATEN, RUB, SINTEC, SSTC-NRS, SURO, TRACTEBEL, TUS, UNIROMA1, VTT, PSI, JRC. SASPAM-SA started on the 1st October 2022 and the planned duration is 48 months; the overall cost is 4 276 038.85 Euros. On 27th August 2021, SASPAM-SA obtained the NUGENIA label that recognizes the excellence of the project proposal.

The key objective of the project is to investigate the applicability and transfer of the operating large-LWR reactor knowledge and know-how to the near-term deployment of iPWR, in the view of SA and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) European licensing analyses needs. Four main elements, not addressed in other on-going SMR oriented initiatives, are investigated:

- Identification of plausible SA scenarios for iPWR designs;
- Identification of the conditions in the vessel and in the containment that characterize iPWR SA scenarios and differ significantly from those in large-LWRs;
- Study the applicability of the existing experimental database to iPWR and identify new experimental needs;
- Assess the capability of internationally recognized European and Non-European computational tools (largely used in Europe) to describe the behavior of the most promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios and to predict the resulting radiological impact on- and off-site, taking into account SA special mitigation/management strategies.

The achievement of the overall elements is assured by a consistent and coherent work programme, reflected in the technical Work Packages (WP) structure.

In order to maximize the knowledge transferability and impacts of the project two generic design-concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations in comparison with larger operating reactor, have been selected for the analyses. These two generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features, considered in the most promising designs ready to go on the European market, allowing to assess in a wider way the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the SA phenomena typical of iPWR.

It is not the project's objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the code's applicability to currently favored designs under postulated SA condition.

No PSA considerations will be done in the project due to the generic nature of the reactor concept considered, then the scenarios identified will be characterized in terms of severity but not in terms of probability.

Proposed project outcomes should be supportive for the iPWR licensing process by bringing up key elements of the safety demonstration needed; this will help speeding up the licensing of iPWRs in Europe, as well as the siting processes of these reactors in light of their possible use near densely populated areas. The kick-off meeting of the took place the 12-13 of October 2022 in Bologna, Italy.

DESIGN 1

Generic iPWR characterized by a submerged containment and electric power of about 60 MWe

DESIGN 2

Generic iPWR characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment and an electric power of about 300 MWe

Coordinator's Foreword

Dear Colleagues and Partners,

It is with great enthusiasm that I welcome you to the first issue of the SASPAM-SA project newsletter. This newsletter is meant not only to showcase our technical and scientific progress, but also a way to share the collaborative spirit, passion and vision that unite us.

SASPAM-SA is an European project, where the word together is fully applicable being a shared commitment to address the challenges of advanced nuclear reactor safety through rigorous and conscious approaches. In a time when public trust and technical excellence must go hand in hand, our focus on transparency, cooperation, open access science is a meaningful response.

This newsletter will serve as our periodic meeting point: a window into our results, ongoing activities, and the people who make SASPAM-SA a reality. Our work is driven by a shared vision to make the nuclear energy of the future safer, more resilient, and grounded in scientific knowledge.

Wishing you a good read,

Fulvio Mascari

Coordinator of the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Project
ENEA, Italy

Major Insight from WP2

F. Gabrielli (KIT)

The 'Input deck development and hypothetical SA scenarios assessment' Working Package (WP) 2, coordinated by KIT (Germany), aims at assessing generic, but representative, SA and CFD codes' input decks, analyzing the iPWRs' behavior in postulated Design Basis Accident (DBA) and hypothetical SA conditions, and investigating the codes' capability to simulate the dominant phenomena driving such scenarios. For maximizing knowledge transferability and the impact of the SASPAM-SA project, the 15 partners joining the WP2 focused their work on the analysis of the two generic iPWR concepts considered in the project: the 'Design-1' (60 MWe) with a submerged containment and the 'Design-2' (300 MWe), which employs several passive systems and a dry containment. These two iPWR designs incorporate the main design features of the most promising designs ready for deployment in the European market.

In the framework of the WP2, a set of DBA and SA scenarios are postulated and analyzed by means the state-of-art European and non-European integral (AC2, ASTEC, MELCOR, MAAP, EDF-MAAP) and CFD (containmentFOAM, Ansys CFX) codes. It should be noted that since no Probability Safety Assessment (PSA) considerations are done in the project (generic designs are considered), the SA scenarios are analyzed in terms of severity and not of probability to occur. The sharing of already available datasets and of data significantly improve the efficiency in reaching the milestones of the first year of the WP2 activity. A large calculation campaign has been completed, the preliminary analyses showing that the codes are able to reproduce the main thermal-hydraulics and in-vessel degradation phenomena during the scenarios. Furthermore, the comparison of the results reveals a quite consistent agreement among the codes with respect to the primary variables of the sequences analyzed, i.e., main events timing, hydrogen mass production, and corium mass. A common paper summarizing the WP2 activities of the first year has been submitted at the last ERMSAR conference in Sweden. Furthermore, papers summarizing their own preliminary analyses have been submitted by the partners to different conferences (ERMSAR, NURETH, NUTHOS) and journals. Currently, partners' reports and detailed files including the results from the simulations have been collecting.

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Major Insight from WP3, T. Lind (PSI)

The main objectives of the WP3: “Applicability and Transfer of the Existing severe accident experimental database for iPWR Assessment” are to study the relevance and applicability of the existing experimental database to iPWR, to develop methods to extend the applicability of existing data, and to identify the need for new experiments. The relevant phenomena will be identified and the review of the current experimental database will be done considering the following phenomena: a) In-vessel degradation and coolability; b) Containment; c) ST; d) Ex-vessel (If any ex-vessel phenomenology will be identified in the project).

During the first project year, partners have collected experimental data considered to be of relevance to iPWRs. Data have been collected from a large number of facilities and experimental programs. The facility features and boundary conditions in the experiments have been compared to those of iPWRs, as analysed in WP2 for SASPAM-SA designs 1 and 2. Additional analyses were carried out in WP2 to support review of experimental data in the area of,

e.g., air ingress and related hydrogen risk. The phenomena and experiments which have been selected for review were presented by the partners, and extensively discussed at the first annual SASPAM-SA meeting in Bologna in October, 2023.

To facilitate the review and evaluation of experimental data, a process was proposed which can be followed by the partners in their work (following figure). In the first step, the phenomena to be evaluated will be selected, followed by steps to define experiments, assess the boundary conditions, compare the data with iPWR conditions, and finally distribution of the data to those applicable to iPWRs, those potentially applicable using adaptation methods, and those not applicable.

The work in WP3 continues with the last steps of evaluation of the data, and distribution of the data into the three defined categories. Finally, once the evaluation is ready, possible needs for further experimental work in any of the assessed phenomena will be identified.

Process to review experimental data - draft

Major Insight from WP4 F. Fichot (ASNR)

The activities carried out in WP4 were dedicated to two main tasks:

- 1) Collecting from reactors scenarios (calculated in WP2) all the relevant data for stand-alone in-vessel melt retention calculations.
- 2) Developing a OD model for preliminary evaluations of designs 1 and 2 and for identification of specific features of IVR in this type of SMR.

The first task was completed and data (masses of corium and steel, residual power, geometry of lower plenum) are now available for steady-state and transient calculations of In-Vessel Retention (IVR) in each design. Those calculations will be completed this year.

The second task was completed by UniRoma1: a stand-alone module was developed, both in Matlab and Python, to evaluate the profiles of heat flux and residual thickness along the vessel wall. As expected, the first results show that IVR strategy appears feasible, with a good safety margin. Some specific features of IVR in iPWRs appear: a larger fraction of power transferred to the top of the oxide pool because of the low aspect ratio (shallow pool), the existence of a rather thick oxide crust and the occurrence of a thin metal layer but a limited focusing effect because of a large fraction of power lost by radiative heat transfer.

The next steps will be the detailed and transient calculations with system codes and the proposals for improvements of models to deal with the identified specificities of iPWRs with respect to IVR.

Major Insight from WP6 M. Ilvonen (VTT)

The objective of WP6 (Emergency planning zone, EPZ) is to quantify the radiological risks that might possibly result from hypothetical severe accidents of the Design-1 and Design-2 iPWRs considered in the previous work packages. When considering acceptance and siting of SMRs, the decision-makers and general public will usually want to know estimates of possible accidental radiation doses to the offsite population. In WP6, we will be calculating those estimates first in a conservative way (upper limits of doses, very unlikely to be realized) and then using best-estimate data from WP5 (Containment). To prepare the work, a review phase has been completed during the first project year, looking at currently existing guidelines and regulations, and also available methodology to determine the extent of the EPZ for various plant types and in various countries. In addition to country-specific regulations (e.g. Italy, Lithuania, Ukraine, Bulgaria, Finland), basic EU safety directives were considered. Specifically for SMR plants, the outcomes of the IAEA-facilitated SMR Regulators' Forum were studied, as well as more generally the related IAEA requirements and guidelines. Valuable insights into the EPZ decision-making process were acquired from categorization and SWOT analysis of different principles, like worst case based, risk-based or risk-informed, and generic vs. plant-specific methodology. The basic character of the procedure could be deterministic, probabilistic, or hybrid of those. Possible uses and siting alternatives were considered, as they would usually affect the emergency planning in practice. Attention was paid to specific near-field phenomena in atmospheric dispersion and radiation exposure, as we expect the affected area to be smaller than for current larger LWRs. Suitability of dispersion and dose projection tools, like ARANO, HotSpot, JRODOS, MACCS, RASCAL, and also actual CFD, was preliminarily studied based on their available features. The work serves as a basis for the conservative doses task, which in turn will produce some recommendations for the best-estimate task.

ANNUAL MEETINGS

The kick-off meeting of the SASPAM-SA project has been hosted by ENEA and took place the 12-13th of October in Bologna, Italy.

SASPAM-SA Second Annual Meeting took place the 10-12 of October in CNR Bologna, Via Piero Gobetti, 101, 40129 Bologna. About 120 experts alternate between in-person and remote participation! 70 experts registered in presence! More than 50 contributions presented and discussed along the annual meeting. The first meetings of the Supporting Groups - Advisory Board (AB) and End User Group (EUG) - took place as well.

The SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project, Third Annual Meeting took place in October 14th - 16th, 2024 at IRSN Headquarters, Fontenay-aux-Roses, France. About 70 contributions were presented and discussed during the meeting, covering several important sessions. Additionally, the second meetings of the Supporting Groups - Advisory Board (AB) and End User Group (EUG) took place.

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON SMR SAFETY FOR A SUSTAINABLE SHORT-TERM DEPLOYMENT

October 17th – 18th, 2024
IRSN Headquarter, 31 Av. de la Division Leclerc

F. Mascari (ENEA), A. Bentaib (ASNR),
F. Giannetti (UNIROMA1)

The First SASPAM-SA Open Workshop, officially titled “International Workshop on SMR Safety for a Sustainable Short-term Deployment”, was held on October 17–18, 2024, at the IRSN headquarters in Fontenay-aux-Roses, Paris, France. Organized under the SASPAM-SA Euratom project, the event marked a significant step forward in the collaborative efforts to ensure the safe deployment of Light Water Small Modular Reactors (LW-SMRs) in Europe and beyond. Bringing together more than 60 experts from 14 countries, the workshop created a dynamic platform for researchers, regulators, and industry stakeholders to discuss recent advancements, identify remaining knowledge gaps, and define short-term R&D priorities necessary to support SMR licensing.

Key Topics of the Workshop

The agenda covered a broad spectrum of issues critical to LW-SMR safety, including:

- Accident scenarios and associated phenomenology in LW-SMRs.
- Predictive capabilities of safety computer codes under transient conditions.
- Relevance of current experimental databases to steady-state and transient LW-SMR operation.
- Evaluation of Severe Accident (SA) mitigation strategies, such as In-Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR) and hydrogen management.
- Modeling guidelines and best practices for LW-SMR safety analysis.
- Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) determination tools and their applicability to SMRs.
- High-fidelity analysis tools and their role in safety evaluations.
- Integration of LW-SMRs within hybrid energy systems and associated safety considerations.
- The role of standardization in advancing nuclear safety research for SMRs.

Workshop Outcomes & Proceedings

The workshop succeeded in highlighting critical knowledge gaps and setting out a roadmap for targeted short-term research aimed at accelerating the licensing process for SMRs. It underscored the need for international cooperation, robust modeling practices, and the modernization of safety analysis tools tailored to the unique features of LW-SMRs.

Read the complete proceedings and the full set of workshop presentations is now available online for public viewing: <https://www.saspam-sa.eu/open-workshop/>

1st SASPAM-SA Training on LWR-SMR Safety: From DBA to Severe accident – Phenomena, Experiments, Mitigation Strategies, and Code Application, October 16-17, 2025, Sapienza Congress Center via Salaria 113, Rome, Italy

The 1st SASPAM-SA training aims to contribute to the capacity building needed to support the future licensing and deployment of SMRs in Europe. The training brings together researchers, engineers, and students to deepen their understanding of SMR-specific safety aspects, with a focus on accident phenomenology, mitigation strategies, and the application of state-of-the-art computational tools.

This training event is organized within the framework of the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project and complements the broader dissemination and knowledge-transfer activities ongoing in the European and international SMR community.

The training is designed to provide a comprehensive introduction and hands-on insight into SMR-specific safety challenges, leveraging the findings from SASPAM-SA and related European research initiatives.

Key topics addressed include:

- Accident scenarios and relevant safety phenomena in LWR-SMRs;
- Comparison of safety approaches in SMRs versus large LWRs;
- Severe accident mitigation strategies including In-Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR);
- Use of existing experimental databases to inform SMR safety;
- Emergency Planning Zones (EPZ) and regulatory perspectives for SMRs;
- Application and demonstration of major computational tools (AC2, ASTEC, MAAP, MELCOR, containmentFOAM, etc.) used in the SASPAM-SA project for SMR safety analysis;
- Future perspectives for research and development in SMR safety and licensing support.

The agenda spans theoretical lectures and applied case studies, providing participants with both foundational knowledge and exposure to ongoing advanced research and practical tools.

ENEN2+ Group Mobility Application has been approved for the MS, PhD students and early career professionals.

For more information visit: <https://www.saspam-sa.eu/saspam-sa-1st-training-session/>

Publications

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- Krieger J., Koch M., Stahlberg G. (2024). Analyses of a postulated severe accident in a generic Small Modular Reactor using AC2. Kerntechnik, Leipzig, Germany.
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- Garcia M., Lugo T., Herranz L.E. (2024). The effect of passive safety systems in a generic iPWR design. 50^a Reunión Anual SNE, Córdoba, Spain.
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POSTS AND EVENTS POOLS

#euratom #research #energy #nuclear #nuclearengineering #safety #nuclearsafety #enea #snetp | Fulvio Mascari
Great to meet our Euratom coordinator colleagues during FISA-EURADWASTE 2025 - Claire Vaglio-Gaudard for TANDEM Project + + + + + Michael Montout for Pastels H2020 + + + + + Egidius Urbonavicius for...

#euratom #snetp #enea #research #nuclear #nuclearengineering #engineering #safety...
Happy to be at FISA-EURADWASTE 2025 & SNETP FORUM in Warsaw !<https://lnkd.in/es5-kXVe> #EURATOM...
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#fisa2025 #euratom #nuclearsafety #research #euratom #collaboration #innovation...
Great interaction yesterday between the SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project and the GO-VIKING project...
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Happy to be part of FISA-EURADWASTE 2025 #ENEAEURATOM #SNETP #RESEARCH #ENGINEERING #NUCLEAR #NUCLEARSAFETY #NUCLEARENGINEERING #ENERGY
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#euratom #together #enea #euratom #snetp #research #engineering #nuclear #nuclearsafety #nuclearengineering #energy | Fulvio Mascari
Happy to have contributed to the Plenary IV: "Research And Innovation Supporting Safety, Security And Safeguards" of the FISA-EURADWASTE 2025 & SNETP Forum (https://lnkd.in/v0lsNw_yG) Great discussion and inspiring exchange of ...
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Discover the SASPAM-SA Interview with Coordinator Fulvio Mascari | SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project
SASPAM-SA proudly presents the interview with our coordinator Fulvio Mascari at the SNETP Forum 2024! We're excited to share the exclusive interview with Fulvio Mascari, filmed during the SNETP Forum 2024! This video shines a...
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At Enlit Europe 2023 (<https://lnkd.in/d3iNAap>), TANDEM Project and SASPAM-SA Horizon...

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#smr #nuclear #enlit2023 | SNETP

🌐 Exploring the Future of Energy at Enlit Europe! Join our panel session today happening now & featuring insights from Gilles Quénehervé, Canet Serin, project manager – from the NPhyCo Project Fulvio Mascari, project manager – from the...

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#smr #nuclear #nuclearsafety #saspamsa #euratom #lwr #smr #energy #research #researchanddevelopment #engineering #nuclearengineering...

It was a real pleasure to attend and contribute to the INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR ON NUCLEAR REACTOR CORE THERMAL-HYDRAULICS ANALYSIS (ISRECTHA-2 - https://lnkd.in/dic_5uNk), POLIMI, 28-30 July, Lecco (Italy) 🌍...

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Together – driven by passion, inspired by happiness, research is the engine of plant safety.

**FIRST PASTELS-SASPAM-SA
Joint meeting
15 November 2023**

Funded by the European Union

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Today we had the first PASTELS-SASPAM-SA meeting, at this first stage restricted only to the two Consortium Parties, focused to provide an overview of the research activities carried out in Pastels H2020 project along its implementation and the...

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The first SASPAM-SA/PASTELS meeting took place yesterday restricted, for now, only to the two Consortium members. The latter provided an overview of the research activities carried out in Pastels H2020 project along its implementation a...

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Happy to share with you that our Coordinator, Fulvi...

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#collaboration #international | Sanjeev Gupta

It was great to see all colleagues in a face-to-face meeting of IPRESCA after a gap ...

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NURETH-20 Third DAY! The contribution continue!! Participation and co-charing of the panel discussion about "Beyond Design Basis Accidents in Advanced Reactors: Opportunity and Challenges", Session Chair: David Luxat Session Organizer: Davi ...

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SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project posted on LinkedIn
 SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project posted images on LinkedIn

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Dear Colleagues, we are happy to share with you that our Coordinator, Fulvio Mascari, has been invited at the conference "New Trends of Nuclear Reactors: Small Modular Reactors. Experience of Leading Countries and Developers"...

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#snetforum2023 #nuclearenergy #snetp #saspam_sa #research #engineering #nuclearenergy #nuclearsafety #nuclear #euratom #smr...

SASPAM-SA at the SnetpForum2023! #SnetpForum2023 #nuclearenergy #snetp #SASPAM_SA #research #engineering #nuclearenergy #nuclearsafety #nuclear #EURATOM #SMR #projects

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SASPAM-SA at the SNETP FORUM 2023 presented by our Coordinator Fulvio Mascari: 23 partners from 13 European countries are part of SASPAM-SA: universities, research institutes, TSO, industrials and engineering organizations.

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Dear Colleagues, happy to share with you that yesterday there was a meeting, organized by EC Euratom Research, to identify some research topics of common interest for water cooled reactors between USNRC and Euratom Research funds...

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#research #engineering #nuclearenergy #nuclearsafety #nuclear #nuclearpower #euratom #smr #enea #projects #experience #share I...

Dear Colleagues, we are happy to share with you that our Coordinator, Fulvio Mascari (ENEA), has been invited to participate at H2020 PASTELS Workshop at Erlangen hosted by FRA-G on the 22nd and 23rd of March, 2023.

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#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment #nuclearengineering...

https://lnkd.in/d_4vGG7T #nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment #nuclearengineerin...

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FUEL MATRIX

#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment #engineering #nuclearenergy #nuclearsafety #nuclear #euratom...

Dear Colleagues, I'm happy to share with you that SASPY^EU (<https://lnkd.in/dQ1Y1P6U>), helped me to explain in a easy way, the barriers confining the fission products for water reactors at power operation: — the fuel...

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EMUG European MELCOR User Group | SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project

Dear Colleagues, we are happy to share with you that the first technical insights from the SASPAM-SA activity, relate...

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Dear Colleagues, we are happy to share with you that today our Coordinator, Fulvio Mascari (ENEA), has been invited to participate at the Coordinators' hub Day, 14 March 2023 <https://lnkd.in/dg8PQZEW> contributing to a panel discussion with other...

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#together #smr #nuclear #nuclearsafety #saspamsa #euratom #iwr #smr #energy #research #researchanddevelopment #engineering...

Proud to represent the SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project and to photograph our brilliant young researchers at the SERAFIN Workshop, hosted by ENEA! Great energy, great science, great people, great results #together!

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#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment #nuclearengineering #nuclearsafety #nuclear #nuclearesearch...

Happy to be at the NUTHOS-14 conference (<https://nuthos-14.org/>) and meet colleagues and friends..... together with SASPY^EU !!

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#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment
#nuclearengineering #nuclearsafety #nuclear #nuclearresearch...

✨ Great to have been at the ERMSAR conference <https://lnkd.in/eg4FHbah!> ✨
Happy to have met several friends and proud of the SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project contribution at the conference! Stay tuned for more updates and highlights...

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SASPAM-SA Acknowledgement/Disclaimer

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Swiss Confederation
ME-INT2023-EVT2304138

Fulvio Mascari

#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment
#nuclearengineering #nuclearsafety #nuclear #nuclearresearch...

Happy to participate at the Interregional Workshop on Experimental Testing and Validation for Design and Safety Analysis Computer Codes for Small Modular Reactors, IAEA Headquarter, Vienna, Austria, 18–21 June...

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Happy Easter

#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment
#nuclearengineering #nuclearsafety #nuclear #nuclearresearch...

GREAT EASTER BREAK! <https://lnkd.in/eghpqyXq> #nuclearenergy #nuclearpower
#research #researchanddevelopment #nuclearengineering #nuclearsafety #nuclear
#nuclearresearch #engineering #enea #energy #safety #SNETP #EURATOM...

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#nuclearengineering #nuclearsafety #nuclear #nuclearresearch...

Fourth paper presented at the ERMSAR 2024 conference (<https://lnkd.in/eU-U54kP>) from SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project: Analysis of Postulated Severe Accidents in Generic Integral PWR Small Modular Reactors in the frame of the...

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Fall in love with nuclear

#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment... | Fulvio Mascari

BUON SAN VALENTINO!!! <https://lnkd.in/efHJDvH> #nuclearenergy #nuclearpower
#research #researchanddevelopment #nuclearengineering #nuclearsafety #nuclear
#nuclearresearch #engineering #enea #energy #safety #SNETP #EURATOM...

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ERMSAR 2024 | KTH | Fulvio Mascari

Happy to be at ERMSAR 2024 and thanks to the SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project colleagues for their efforts to the project and...

[linkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com)

SNETP Forum - SNETP | Fulvio Mascari

✨ Exciting News! The SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project is all set to participate in the poster session for Communication for Labeled Projects at the SNETP Forum 2024, starting tomorrow! 🎉 A big thank you to Alina Giesler for her outstanding...

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#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment #nuclearengineering #nuclearenergy #nuclearsafety #nuclear...

Dear Colleagues, we wish you and your family a MERRY CHRISTMAS and a Happy NEW YEAR from SASPAM-SA and SASPY^EU.

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#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment #nuclearengineering...

Dear Colleagues, I'm happy to have contributed as...

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#nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #research #researchanddevelopment #engineering #nuclearenergy...

I'm happy to be at Enlit Europe 2023 (<https://lnkd.in/dppmtdZr>), at the EU...

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SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project Second...

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#research #nuclear #nuclearengineering #engineering #nuclearsafety #safety #nuclearenergy #nuclearpower #researchanddevelopment...

NURETH-20: Thanks to Florian Fichot and Jeremy Bitan to have shared the session In-vessel Corium and Debris Bed Coolability.2. #Research #nuclear #nuclearengineering #engineering #nuclearsafety #safety #nuclearenergy...

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Fulvio Mascari posted on LinkedIn

Fulvio Mascari posted images on LinkedIn

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<https://lnkd.in/dpEzf2PT> | SASPAM-SA Horizon Euratom Project

<https://lnkd.in/dpEzf2PT>

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SASPAM-SA SNETP FORUM 2023 | Fulvio Mascari

Dear Colleagues I'm happy to share with you the SASPAM-SA poster presented at the SNETP FORUM 2023. I want to underline the importance of SNETP and, in particular, of the Technical Areas as a platform where the technical community ca...

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#sasam_sa #research #engineering #nuclearenergy #nuclearsafety
 #nuclear #nuclearpower #euratom #smr #enea #sasam_sa | Fulvio...
 I'm happy to have attended the meeting and to have presented the SASPAM-SA
 Horizon Euratom Project (to have more information: #SASPAM_SA and
 https://lnkd.in/dDg5q_ry) and to have presented the activity done in the passive...
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QR Codes

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